

Cooperative development and human interface of a computer algebra system with the Fōrmulæ framework

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Cooperative development of a computer algebra system (CAS) with the Fōrmulæ framework is based in modularity, it is, by the independent development of pieces that can be published, final users can choose and download a set of them and finally inserted in a base system, in which these modules can dynamically interoperate with others. Such these modules could be written by different people, places and times. There should not be required that these people or teams be managed by a central instance, instead they write programs based on a specification.

Traditionally, creating a CAS is much like creating a programming language. It must be previously fully designed and this process involves the creation of its grammar. All the programs or snippets created for such that language must be compliant with the syntax in order to be compiled or run, and since the creation of the program is usually given as code in form of text, parsers are needed in order to check the text against the grammar.

In the Fōrmulæ framework there is no a formal syntax, so there is no grammar. Every structure is dynamically defined, even the basic ones, like numbers, symbols, statements, etc.

The Fōrmulæ framework provides a set of especificaions for writing interoperable modules in three different aspects: *visualization*, *edition* and *reduction*.

Visualization

An immediate benefit of modular pieces of code is provided for visualization. There are expressions with different form of visualization, and none of them is preferable to other because the decision depends on the field of application, personal preference or even localization (i.e. the sine function in Spanish is abbreviated as *sen* (from *seno*). Two o more ways of visualization can be downloaded and installed and the user could choose which of them he or she wants to use, for example, there could be two independent modules for programming, one is intended to show programming elements as a flowchart, and the other one to show elements in a traditional, indented list of statements.

Visualization is performed in a graphic style, the expressions are shown in a pretty-print fashion which is more natural and close to how human are accustomed. for example, instead of showing the following piece of text such like

$(-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}) / (2a)$, the expression can be seen in a natural way as:

$$\frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad (1)$$

Edition

Usually, the input for a CAS session is provided as a text line, which has to be parsed for syntax verification before it could be processed. Sometimes its syntax is so complex that several CAS and/or programming languages have been informally qualified as *write-only languages*.

Under Förmulæ framework, the input is always an expression, the building of a particular input is a process of transforming an expression, adding, replacing or removing subexpressions, so no parsing is needed. An expression is always well formed. It strongly relies on the *null* expression. This simple expression resembles the zero in our numeral system, it means none by itself, but it provides structure on the positional nature and its discovery represents a great historical advance for humankind.

As an example, suppose there is a simple expression, a number:

$$5 \quad (2)$$

Then, there is the intention of creating an addend for this expression, say another number. By any method the addition operation is performed (choosing from a menu, pushing a button, pressing the '+' key, etc.) It must be impossible to create the following *pseudo* expression:

$$5+ \quad (3)$$

Instead the following is obtained. The square is used here to represent the *null* expression.

$$5 + \square \quad (4)$$

Finally, the null expression is selected, and by any other method the second number is created, which replaces the currently selected expression (the null expression) leaving the the result:

$$5 + 2 \quad (5)$$

By this simple method is possible to create complex expressions, in a way that in every step, the expression being built is always well formed.

Reduction

Reduction is a transformation of an expression to another one, usually simpler, which is considered more useful. Reduction is also modular, and no exclusive, that is, a given kind of expression can have zero, one or multiple reducers associated to it.

As a very simple example, the expression $2 + 3$ can be transformed (or reduced) to the expression 5 because there is a reducer associated with the *addition* expression -among other reducers associated to this- that *knows* how to sum numeric addends.

As a second example, the following expression is syntactically valid:

$$\frac{\textit{the mars planet}}{\textit{the Hg chemical element}} \quad (6)$$

But it surely will not be transformed in another expressions because it is very improbable that a developer had the intention of writing a reducer for it that makes sense, because the expression has no semantic validity.

Every computable operation can be written as a reducer, and there is an algorithm for apply a set of relevant reducers in order to transform complex expressions, it is called *the reduction engine* and it is implemented as part of the Förmulæ framework. Most of the functionality commonly provided for known CAS are able to be written as reduction modules.

New modules can appear in order to improve the older ones -in a schema of evolution-, or to add new ways of reduction. As an example, the Risch algorithms [1] is a method for mechanical calculation of antiderivates (for a wide range of mathematical functions). In a certain point it requires a particular solution of the constant problem, that is, to test if a certain expression is equal to zero. This problem is under certain circumstances undecidable, so the effectiveness of the Risch algorithm depends of the ability to solve -formally or heuristically- the constant problem for a specific expression. Several new or improved methods of solution of the constant problem can emerge as reduction modules that can be added to the base system, making our method of symbolic integration dynamically and gradually stronger.

Implications

It opens new possibilities for interoperate with different paradigms in a single CAS, i.e. talking about programming, since someone can write modules for different programming paradigms, it is possible to build programs or snippets with a mixture of styles, such as structured, object oriented, functional, declarative, logical, parallel,

etc. Other solutions can be transported to such an interoperable methodology, for example, proof assistants and theorem provers.

There are certain computing science implications, the dynamic nature of defining, creating and implement functionality implies a creation of a ontology (a dynamic one) and it also affects the known methods of representation and transfer or knowledge

According to the results of Kurt Gödel and Alan Turing, there cannot exist a both complete and consistent system for fundamental mathematics and computability. Going further, Gregory Chaitin [2] asserts that the concept of *truth* is not absolute, it could either change with time, be sometimes random and even be accidental. In consequence, as it is impossible to eventually create a complete/consistent monolithic CAS, we must start to focus on dynamic, cooperative methods of developement.

References

- [1] R. H Risch, *The problem of integration in finite terms*, pp. 167-189 (1969).
- [2] Gregory Chaitin, *Meta Math! The Quest for Omega*, (2005).